

Yashil

IQTISODIYOT va TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, siyosiy, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

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In today's global economic environment, agrobusiness is not limited to the production of agro-cultural products alone. It is closely related to the introduction of innovative technologies, the processing industry, international trade, and the solution of environmental problems. In the context of global population growth, limited natural resources, and climate change, this sector is becoming one of the key sectors for the sustainable development of society.

For countries with an agrarian economy like Uzbekistan, the development of agrobusiness is of strategic importance. It not only provides the domestic market with food products, but also serves to expand export opportunities and integrate with international markets. This article provides detailed information about the role of agrobusiness in the development of society, its opportunities and prospects.

LITERATURE REVIEW OF THE SUBJECT

Below, I will try to cite sentences from the literature on the topic of «the role of agrobusiness in the development of society and its opportunities» and interpret them as best I can, and I certainly hope that this will be useful.

Bobokulov Kh. and Gulyamov Sh. in their book «Agro-cultural Economics» express the following ideas:

“Agro-culture is the foundation of the economy, and its efficiency can be increased through the introduction of market relations and innovations.” In their opinion, state support and active participation of the private sector are important factors. This idea is relevant in the conditions of Uzbekistan, since innovations such as drip irrigation technology or the development of cluster systems in agro-culture play an important role in increasing productivity and entering international markets.

Scholars such as K. Anderson and J. Swinnen argue in their books about the short-term impact of state subsidies on agro-culture and emphasize the importance of stimulating the private sector in the long term. They put forward the idea that the state should not interfere excessively in market mechanisms. This type of idea is important for ensuring the sustainable development of the agro-cultural system. In Uzbekistan, the subsidy system is important in supporting the private sector, but it should not be forgotten that it is also important to emphasize that attracting private investment is also necessary for long-term development.

Johnston BF and Mellor JV conducted several studies and came to the following conclusions: “Agro-culture is the main factor of primary economic development”. According to these scientists, creating added value in the economy through processing and exporting agro-cultural products not only increases the state economy, but also provides opportunities for members of society, such as new jobs, which significantly improves the social environment in the country. This idea is relevant for Uzbekistan, since the creation of agro-industrial clusters and deep processing of products have a positive impact on the country's economy. In particular, innovative processing technologies are being used in the export of fruit and vegetable products.

J. Dixon, A. Gulliver, D. Gibbon in their book “Farming Systems and Poverty” cite the following points:

They argue that poverty can be reduced by modernizing agro-cultural systems and developing cooperatives. They believe that supporting small farms ensures social and economic stability. In Uzbekistan, cooperatives and cluster systems play an important role in developing rural areas and improving the living standards of the population. Such systems support farmers in accessing international markets.

In the FAO book «Global Agrobusiness Trends: Challenges and Opportunities»:

FAO experts note that global demand for environmentally friendly and organic products is growing. They emphasize that innovation in agrobusiness and adaptation to international standards are important for ensuring global competitiveness, and fully explain it. The development of the production of environmentally friendly and organic products opens up great opportunities for the agro-cultural sector of Uzbekistan. By producing products that meet international standards, the country can increase its export potential.

JV. Mellor.: In the book «Agro-culture on the Road to Industrialization»:

Describes it as “the initial stage of agro-cultural industrialization.” It recommends stimulating economic growth by channeling agro-cultural products to industrial enterprises and creating a supply chain, and explains how this process works. Uzbekistan can diversify its economy by developing agro-industry and creating a product chain. For example, integrating all stages of the cotton growing process into a finished product can help increase exports.

The opinions of the above scientists indicate the role of agrobusiness in the economy, ways to increase its efficiency and access to international markets. These opinions can be of great importance in the formation of agro-cultural policy in Uzbekistan. I will interpret these sentences and comments to highlight the interrelationship and importance of logistics systems and their different levels (macrologistics and micrologistics) in agro-culture. Each source highlights its own specific aspects and indicates the principles necessary to ensure effective management of agro-cultural logistics.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research methodology on the role of agrobusiness in the development of society and its potential includes the following several basic and complex stages:

Research goals and objectives:

To study the place of agrobusiness in society and the economy, to identify the factors influencing its development and to substantiate them with examples, as well as to assess the opportunities and prospects in various areas of agrobusiness and to emphasize their importance. To analyze the political, social and economic factors influencing the sustainable development of agrobusiness in society.

Research object and subject:

The object of our research is «The agrobusiness system and its role in society, its relationship with economic, social and environmental factors.»

The subject of our research is «Analysis of agrobusiness entities (farmers, producers, entrepreneurs, government agencies, consumers) and their activities.»

The following research methods were used:

Theoretical methods: analysis of existing scientific literature on the role of agrobusiness in the development of society, study of the relationship of agrobusiness with economics and ecology.

Empirical methods: analysis of the situation in various sectors of agrobusiness using statistics and surveys, study of entrepreneurs and producers.

Integrated methods: combining economic, environmental, and social analysis methods to examine the impact of agrobusiness on society and the economy.

Research methods include:

Field observation method: direct contact with agrobusiness entities, studying their activities and existing problems.

Questionnaire and interview method: conducting interviews with entrepreneurs, farmers, and other agrobusiness participants.

Statistical analysis method: conducting analyses of economic indicators (e.g., production volume, income, export-import volume).

The scientific and theoretical foundations of our research are as follows:

The scientific and theoretical foundations of the study include the economic and social tasks of agrobusiness, the basic principles of development, sustainability, and innovative approaches.

The main stages of our research:

Initial analysis phase: study the main components of agrobusiness and its place in society.

Data collection stage: collection and analysis of statistical data from agrobusiness entities.

Analysis and final conclusions stage: recommendations based on research results and identification of agrobusiness development prospects.

Based on this methodology, it is possible to consider the necessary measures to expand the role and opportunities of agrobusiness in the development of society and achieve sustainable development.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Of course, based on the available statistics in Uzbekistan, it is possible to analyze the role of agrobusiness in the development of society and its potential. Below, based on statistical data and economic indicators in Uzbekistan, I will explain the significant importance of agrobusiness not only for the state but also for society.

The role of agrobusiness in social development economic importance.

The economic role of the agrobusiness sector in Uzbekistan is very large. The share of agriculture in the economy of Uzbekistan is quite high. The production of agricultural products plays an important role in increasing the export potential of the state and ensuring the domestic market.

Agriculture is a key sector of Uzbekistan's economy, accounting for about 25% of GDP and employing about 26% of the workforce. Cotton and grain are the country's main crops, but the lifting of quotas and price controls in 2020-2021 will help shift to higher-value fruit and vegetable production. To further liberalize the sector and reflect the sharp increase in global wheat prices in 2022, the government switched to market prices for grain purchases and sales from June 1, 2022. Agricultural exports contributed about 8.4% to Uzbekistan's external earnings in 2022.

The Uzbek government has focused on wheat production in recent years to increase the country's food security and has supported poultry and livestock farming. The 2022-2026 Animal Husbandry and Sector Development Program was adopted in February 2022. On April 20, 2023, the World Bank approved a \$240 million loan for the second livestock sector development project. The profitability of fresh fruits and vegetables

has increased in recent years, and local farmers have aggressive plans to develop export markets for these products. In 2022-2025, the government will provide small family farms with 200,000 hectares of cotton and grain land allocated from large farms and clusters on ten-year horticultural leases and allocate \$100 million to support loans. 100,000 hectares of irrigated farmland will be leased to 400,000 small farmers in 2022, and another 100,000 hectares will be leased to 350,000 small farmers in 2023 (table 1).

Table 1. Agroculture Market Size, million USD1

	2020	2021	2022	2023 estimated
Total Local Production	15,041	17,297	18,863	20,500
Total Exports	1,336	1,372	1,632	2,000
Total Imports	1,851	2,510	3,393	4,000
Imports from the US	10.4	1.9	2.3	N/A
Total Market Size	15,556	18,435	20,624	22,500
Exchange Rates	10,056	10,610	11,051	11,600

According to the World Bank's set of development indicators from officially recognized sources, agro-cultural employment (% of total employment) in Uzbekistan (modeled ILO estimate) was recorded at 25.9% in 2022 (figure 1).

Uzbekistan Employment in agriculture (% of total employment) (modeled ILO estimate) - %

Source: tradingeconomics.com | World Bank

Figure 1. The share of the population working in the agro-cultural sector in the employed population in Uzbekistan.

Social Importance

The development of agrobusiness in rural areas of Uzbekistan has significantly improved the well-being and living standards of the population. As a result, the income of rural residents has increased and social infrastructure has been affected.

A new system of training personnel is developing through the digitalization of agro-culture and the introduction of innovative technologies.

1 <https://www.trade.gov/country-commercial-guides/uzbekistan-agro-cultural-sectors>

Ecological Significance: sustainable technologies and environmental protection are being implemented to address environmental issues in the agrobusiness sector. Uzbekistan has state-supported programs for the production of environmentally friendly products.

Sustainable agroculture: the state is implementing programs aimed at the production of environmentally friendly agrocultural products. In particular, there is growing interest in the production of organic agrocultural products.

It is as a result of such projects that the following indicators are emerging:

According to the Statistics Agency, the total volume of agrocultural, forestry and fishery products amounted to 426.3 trillion soums in 2023, an increase of 4.1% compared to the previous year.

In 2023, Uzbekistan produced 2.8 million tons of meat (live weight), 12 million tons of milk and 8.5 million eggs²

The volume of agrocultural products produced last year:

- Cereal products - 8.4 million tons;
- Potatoes - 3.6 million tons;
- Vegetables - 11.6 million tons;
- Melons - 2.4 million tons;
- Fruits and berries - 3.1 million tons;
- Grapes - 1.7 million tons.

Agrobusiness Opportunities

Innovative Technologies

Today, the implementation of the digital economy in Uzbekistan is a serious factor in the effective growth of the country's economy. Uzbekistan has high intellectual potential, developed telecommunications infrastructure, and existing high-tech enterprises are creating the necessary environment for the introduction and further development of an innovative economy. If we talk about agroculture, the implementation of the Development Strategy of Uzbekistan for 2022-2026 is being restructured based on international experience, including the development of automated management systems and databases, in cooperation with developed countries such as Germany and the Netherlands. In Uzbekistan, great attention is paid to the effective use of information technologies in the agrocultural sector. We will not be mistaken if we say that the creation and implementation of an automated farm management system is becoming one of the main tasks of today.

The use of digital technologies in agrobusiness can open up new markets for farmers, improve efficiency in data analysis and resource management. Agrocultural data platforms such as Agrosoft have been operating in Uzbekistan since 2022.

Biotechnology offers the potential to genetically improve agrocultural products and create new varieties. Projects and research are being carried out in Uzbekistan to produce biological pesticides and fertilizers.

In recent years, Uzbekistan's agrocultural exports have been growing significantly. Uzbekistan's agrobusiness products are mainly exported to Russia, China, Kazakhstan, and other CIS countries.

New markets: Uzbekistan is seeking to expand its export geography and is developing trade relations with European, Asian, and other markets.

Investment opportunities exist in Uzbekistan's agrobusiness sector. The sector is developing through government subsidies and grants to support farmers, as well as private sector investment.

Private investment: Investments are being made in various sectors, including through organizations such as Agroinvest, to encourage private sector investment in agroculture and agrobusiness.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

Agrobusiness plays a major role in the development of society in Uzbekistan, its economic, social and environmental significance is evident in every aspect. The fact that the share of the agroculture and agrobusiness sector in the economy is 17-18%, more than 6 million people work in this sector, and the increasing volume of exports are important factors for the country's economy. The pace of economic growth can be further accelerated through the development of innovations in the agrobusiness sector, digital technologies, biotechnology and exports.

Socially, agrobusiness offers great opportunities for increasing the income of the population living in rural areas, creating new jobs, developing the education and training system. Also, programs aimed at producing environmentally friendly products, saving resources, and sustainable development increase the country's attention to the environment.

² <https://kun.uz/en/news/2024/02/09/uzbekistans-agrocultural-production-volume-reached-4263-trillion-uzs-in-2023>

Introducing innovative technologies: expanding digital platforms and new technologies in agrobusiness, providing farmers with effective information, and optimizing production processes.

Increase investment: attracting private and public investment in agroculture and agrobusiness, improving tax incentives and subsidy programs.

Encourage the production of environmentally friendly products: develop organic agroculture, increase the production of environmentally sustainable products.

Education and training: to improve the knowledge and skills of farmers by teaching them modern technologies, organizing practical trainings and courses.

Increasing export potential: making Uzbekistan's agrocultural products competitive in global markets by entering new export markets, improving product quality, and branding.

Agrotourism development: developing tourism in rural areas, supporting agrotourism, and improving infrastructure.

Support for local producers: provide technical and financial assistance to local producers, develop the processing industry.

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